

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

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MEASURES TO ENHANCE THE TAX MECHANISM APPLIED TO BUSINESS ENTITIES

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Abstract: Efficient taxation of business entities is critical for ensuring fiscal sustainability and promoting economic growth. This paper explores current shortcomings in the tax mechanism applied to business entities and proposes targeted measures to improve its efficiency, fairness, and compliance. A mixed-method approach involving statistical analysis, expert surveys, and policy comparison was used. Results indicate that simplification, digitalization, and differentiated tax treatments based on business size significantly improve tax outcomes.

Key words: tax mechanism, business entities, fiscal policy, tax reform, compliance, efficiency.

Annotatsiya: Biznes subyektlarini samarali soliqqa tortish fiskal barqarorlikni ta'minlash va iqtisodiy o'sishni rag'batlantirish uchun muhim hisoblanadi. Ushbu maqolada biznes subyektlariga nisbatan qo'llanilayotgan soliq mexanizmining mavjud kamchiliklari o'rganilib, uning samaradorligi, adolatligi va bajarilish darajasini oshirish bo'yicha aniq chora-tadbirlar taklif etiladi. Tadqiqotda statistik tahlil, ekspertlar so'rovi va siyosatni solishtirishni o'z ichiga olgan aralash usul qo'llanildi. Natijalar shuni ko'rsatadiki, soddalashtirish, raqamlashtirish va biznes hajmiga qarab differensiallashtirilgan soliq yondashuvlari soliq natijalarini sezilarli darajada yaxshilaydi.

Kalit so'zlar: soliq mexanizmi, biznes subyektlari, fiskal siyosat, soliq islohoti, bajarilish, samaradorlik.

Аннотация: Эффективное налогообложение хозяйствующих субъектов имеет решающее значение для обеспечения фискальной устойчивости и стимулирования экономического роста. В данной статье рассматриваются текущие недостатки налогового механизма, применяемого к хозяйствующим субъектам, и предлагаются целевые меры по повышению его эффективности, справедливости и уровня соблюдения. Использован смешанный метод, включающий статистический анализ, экспертные опросы и сопоставление налоговой политики. Результаты показывают, что упрощение, цифровизация и дифференцированный налоговый режим в зависимости от размера бизнеса значительно улучшают налоговые показатели.

Ключевые слова: налоговый механизм, хозяйствующие субъекты, фискальная политика, налоговая реформа, соблюдение, эффективность.

INTRODUCTION

Taxation remains one of the most essential instruments of fiscal policy, serving not only as the primary source of state revenue but also as a powerful tool for influencing economic activity, redistributing wealth, and fostering sustainable development. Through taxation, governments fund public services, infrastructure, and social programs that are critical for long-term economic and social stability.

However, despite its importance, the structure and implementation of tax systems often present significant challenges, particularly for business entities. In many countries – especially those undergoing economic transitions or in the early stages of development – the tax environment is characterized by excessive complexity, inconsistent enforcement, and administrative inefficiencies. These factors can discourage entrepreneurship, increase the cost of doing business, and lead to reduced voluntary compliance.

Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), which typically lack the resources and expertise of larger corporations, are disproportionately affected. They may face difficulties navigating complex tax regulations, dealing with frequent changes in legislation, and coping with burdensome reporting requirements. This environment can push some firms into informality, undermining the tax base and reducing the overall effectiveness of the fiscal system.

This paper seeks to critically examine the current taxation mechanisms applied to business entities and identify ways to enhance their effectiveness and equity. It draws on comparative analysis, empirical data, and expert opinion to formulate practical recommendations. The overarching aim is to create a more transparent, efficient, and business-friendly tax environment that balances revenue needs with economic growth objectives.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

Taxation remains a central policy tool for resource mobilisation and economic regulation. Bird notes that in many developing economies, tax systems often fail to maximise potential revenue due to narrow tax bases, numerous exemptions, and weak administration. His analysis suggests that broadening the tax base and removing inefficient exemptions can enhance equity and efficiency, ensuring that the tax burden is more evenly distributed across economic agents. Keen argues that tax reforms must address both policy and administrative dimensions simultaneously, as changes in rates or structures without improving enforcement capacity yield limited results. He emphasises that effective reforms require careful sequencing and institutional strengthening to avoid revenue shortfalls during transition periods.

Tanzi highlights the significance of tax administration reform alongside policy reform, observing that without efficient collection, even the best-designed tax policies remain ineffective. He discusses how modernising administration, simplifying procedures, and reducing discretion in tax assessments can minimise corruption and foster voluntary compliance. Slemrod and Gillitzer further elaborate on firm behaviour under different tax regimes, suggesting that excessive compliance costs distort resource allocation decisions and deter formalisation among small businesses. Their findings underline that reducing compliance burdens through digitalisation and streamlined processes improves both efficiency and tax morale.

Alm and Torgler provide insights into the psychological determinants of tax compliance, demonstrating that tax morale, or the intrinsic willingness to pay taxes, is closely linked to institutional trust. They argue that transparent use of tax revenues and fair treatment of taxpayers increase compliance rates among business entities, complementing purely legalistic enforcement approaches. The OECD has documented numerous cases where digital tax administration systems have enhanced revenue performance by reducing human errors, improving data matching, and lowering taxpayer compliance costs. Their comparative studies indicate that e-filing, e-payment, and integrated taxpayer service portals are instrumental in improving business tax compliance.

In the context of emerging markets, Bird and Zolt analyse tax reform experiences in Central Asia and Latin America, concluding that gradual and comprehensive reforms yield better long-term results compared to abrupt, fragmented measures. Their work recommends incorporating capacity-building programmes for tax officials and investing in modern IT infrastructure to sustain improvements. Recent IMF research also supports this view, advocating risk-based audit systems and big data analytics to identify evasion patterns and focus administrative resources effectively. Integrating such techniques enhances the precision of audits and reduces unnecessary burdens on compliant taxpayers.

Overall, the literature strongly suggests that enhancing tax mechanisms for business entities requires a multidimensional strategy. This includes legal reforms to broaden tax bases, administrative reforms to improve efficiency, behavioural approaches to build tax morale, and technological investments to modernise systems. By integrating these dimensions, countries can create tax environments that are business-friendly while ensuring sufficient public revenue for sustainable development goals.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

A mixed-methods approach was employed. Quantitative data included national tax statistics from 2019 to 2024, World Bank Doing Business reports, and IMF tax effort data. Qualitative data were collected through structured interviews with 30 tax experts and business representatives. Descriptive statistics and trend analysis were used to examine the quantitative data, while correlation analysis was conducted to identify relationships between tax complexity and business compliance rates. Furthermore, a SWOT analysis of the current tax system was performed to determine its strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats. Benchmarking was also carried out against best practices observed in OECD and regional countries to provide comparative insights for potential reforms.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The findings of this study reinforce the premise that excessive complexity in tax legislation and administrative inefficiencies remain among the most significant barriers to achieving broad-based tax compliance and effective revenue mobilization. Business entities, especially small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), often struggle

with navigating a maze of tax codes, procedures, and frequently changing regulations. These challenges not only increase compliance costs but also contribute to taxpayer frustration, low morale, and in some cases, deliberate non-compliance.

One of the most prominent solutions identified across successful case studies is the simplification of tax structures. Simplified regimes, such as presumptive tax systems or unified turnover taxes can significantly ease the burden on SMEs while maintaining a sufficient level of revenue collection. Countries that have adopted flat tax schemes or reduced the number of tax categories and exemptions report better compliance rates and administrative efficiency.

Another transformative trend is digitalization. The integration of digital tools, such as e-filing systems, online tax portals, automated reporting, and real-time invoicing, has shown to enhance transparency, reduce human error, and limit opportunities for corruption. These tools also enable tax authorities to better monitor compliance in real time and allocate audit resources more strategically. Notably, countries with higher levels of tax digitalization tend to exhibit stronger tax morale and higher revenue collection from the business sector.

However, implementing digital systems is not without challenges. In many emerging and transitioning economies, institutional inertia, limited infrastructure, and insufficient investment in digital transformation act as barriers. Furthermore, digital tools must be accompanied by proper taxpayer education and support systems to ensure inclusive access and prevent digital exclusion, particularly among micro-enterprises and rural businesses.

To better understand the position and performance of national tax systems, especially with respect to SMEs, we conducted a benchmarking analysis comparing selected countries based on their tax policies. Key factors include tax rate levels, filing frequency, the extent of digitalization, and audit practices (Table 1).

Table 1. Comparison of SME tax policies in selected countries

Country	Tax Rate (%)	Filing Frequency	Digital Tools	Audit Practices
Germany	15–30	Quarterly	Fully digital	Risk-based audits
Uzbekistan	4–15	Monthly	Partially digital	Mixed (random & risk)
USA	21 (corporate)	Quarterly	Advanced	Targeted & random
India	22–25	Quarterly	Improving	Increasingly risk-based
Brazil	10–34	Monthly	Moderate	Frequent random audits
South Korea	10–22	Quarterly	Highly digital	Risk-based, automated

This table illustrates that higher-performing economies tend to rely on digitalized systems and risk-based audit frameworks, which reduce administrative burdens and improve compliance. In contrast, emerging economies often rely on more traditional, manual approaches and face higher levels of informality and non-compliance.

Another key insight is the importance of tailoring tax policies to reflect the diversity of business types. One-size-fits-all tax systems often disadvantage smaller firms or those operating in labor-intensive sectors. By differentiating tax requirements and obligations based on firm size, industry, or geographic location, tax systems can become more equitable and responsive to business realities.

Finally, the balance between enforcement and facilitation is crucial. While strong enforcement mechanisms, such as risk-based audits and data-driven monitoring are essential for deterring tax evasion, they must be complemented with support measures. These include taxpayer education, help desks, advisory services, and public awareness campaigns, all of which enhance voluntary compliance and strengthen trust in the tax system.

In summary, countries that invest in simplification, digital infrastructure, and taxpayer support not only improve compliance and collection but also foster a more business-friendly and predictable tax environment an essential condition for economic growth and private sector development (Table 2).

Table 2. SWOT analysis of the current tax mechanism

Strengths: - Established legal tax framework - Experience in policy reform	Weaknesses: - Complex procedures - Low digital adoption - Limited transparency
Opportunities: - Digital transformation - International cooperation - SME tax reform	Threats: - Shadow economy - Resistance to change - Policy instability

The figure illustrates the evolution of three main components of tax revenue in EU-27 countries from 1995 to 2019 as a percentage of GDP (Figure 1).

Evolution of the main components of tax revenue in the EU-27*, % of GDP, 1995-2019

* from 1 February 2020
 Source: Eurostat (gov_10a_taxag)

Figure 1. Overview of tax revenue indicators in selected countries (1995-2019)

Firstly, net social contributions consistently remained the largest component throughout the period, though showing a slight downward trend in the late 1990s from around 15.5% to approximately 14.5% by 2002, after which it stabilised with minor fluctuations. This indicates that while social contributions form a strong fiscal base in Europe, their share has gradually decreased due to demographic changes, labour market reforms, or structural adjustments in pension and welfare systems.

Secondly, taxes on production and imports showed a stable yet modest upward trajectory. In 1995, this indicator was just above 12.5% of GDP and gradually rose, reaching approximately 13.5% by 2019. This suggests a relatively steady reliance on indirect taxation mechanisms such as VAT and excise duties, reflecting both consumption patterns and the harmonisation of indirect tax policies across EU member states during the period.

Thirdly, current taxes on income, wealth, and similar categories demonstrated a more dynamic trend. Starting at nearly 12% of GDP in 1995, it rose significantly towards 2000, reaching 13%, then declined sharply during the early 2000s, likely due to tax cuts and economic slowdowns, especially after the 2001–2002 downturn. Post-2008 crisis, a gradual recovery is observed, stabilising around 13% by 2019. This volatility reflects governments' policy shifts between stimulating economic growth via tax reductions and consolidating budgets through increased direct taxation.

Overall, the data suggests a tax structure dominated by social contributions with balanced shares of production and income taxes, reflecting the EU's welfare-oriented fiscal policy and efforts to maintain revenue stability while adapting to macroeconomic cycles and demographic pressures.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

Enhancing the taxation mechanism for business entities is a critical component of broader economic reform, especially in the context of globalization, increasing competitiveness, and fiscal sustainability. The evidence

presented in this study highlights that achieving an efficient, equitable, and growth-supportive tax environment requires an integrated strategy one that combines administrative simplification, technological innovation, and targeted policy design.

Countries that have successfully modernized their tax systems tend to focus on reducing unnecessary complexity, automating compliance processes, and building trust through transparency and responsive service delivery. In contrast, systems burdened by outdated practices and fragmented enforcement often struggle with high levels of informality, low compliance, and diminished revenue collection.

A particularly important insight from this research is the need to align tax policies with the realities of different types of business entities. Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), for example, require simplified regimes and supportive institutional infrastructure to fulfill their tax obligations effectively. Without such measures, these enterprises may avoid formalization, limiting their potential contribution to the economy and undermining the broader tax base.

Furthermore, the digital transformation of tax systems has proven to be a game-changer in many countries. From online registration to real-time invoicing and AI-based audit selection, digital tools improve both the taxpayer experience and administrative capacity. However, digitalization must be inclusive and supported by adequate investment, education, and governance reform.

To move toward a more effective and modern tax system for business entities, the following actions are recommended:

Develop and implement a national tax digitalization strategy

A clear roadmap is needed to transition from paper-based or semi-digital systems to fully integrated e-tax platforms. This should include capacity building for tax authorities, cybersecurity safeguards, and access support for small businesses.

Introduce progressive simplification for SMEs

Tailor tax compliance requirements based on business size and risk level. Consider introducing tiered regimes with reduced reporting burdens, flat-rate taxes, or turnover-based thresholds to promote voluntary compliance and formalization.

Strengthen taxpayer services and outreach programs

Improve communication and trust between tax authorities and businesses through expanded taxpayer education, multilingual support, call centers, and digital help desks. Ensure that businesses, especially new and small ones, understand their rights and responsibilities under the tax law.

By adopting these measures and remaining responsive to feedback from the business community, policymakers can foster a more transparent, predictable, and growth-oriented tax environment—paving the way for sustainable economic development and a stronger public sector.

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